

FOODITY

Qualitative Analysis of Funding Experiences: Informing the FOODITY Fund

Prepared by F6S

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The FOODITY project

The main goal of FOODITY is to create a European ecosystem of digital solutions that contributes to a more sustainable and healthy food and nutrition system — respecting citizens' rights to personal data sovereignty.

FOODITY will run a **2M€ pilot development programme for creating 12 data-driven solutions** to demonstrate the potential of data-driven innovation in food and nutrition while guaranteeing the user's full control and ownership over their personal data.

These innovations will provide novel solutions to existing research and technical challenges to achieve the four Food 20301 (the EU's research and innovation policy to build better food systems by 2030) key priorities: (1) Nutrition for sustainable and healthy diets, (2) Food systems supporting a healthy planet, (3) Circularity and resource efficiency, and (4) Innovation and empowering communities.

Participants in the pilot development programme will be selected through two open calls to be launched in July and October 2023, respectively. Eligible beneficiaries will be research and technology organisations (RTOs) and universities, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), social innovation actors and training organisations.

The programme will provide its beneficiaries with a set of value-added services: from one-to-one mentoring to training on technical, business, and legal matters, as well as technical and financial support (up to 187.500€ per beneficiary) for developing their pilots.

During the next 3 years (January 2023 - December 2025), the FOODITY consortium, comprised of 7 partners, will join forces to make this a reality.

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Executive Summary

This report presents a qualitative analysis of interviews conducted with six startups and four mentors and investors operating mainly in the food and nutrition sectors, with the aim of informing the design of the future FOODITY Fund.

The analysis identifies key challenges faced by startups in existing funding programmes and accelerators, along with their desired support mechanisms. Key themes include bureaucratic and administrative burden, training and cohort misalignment, gap from innovation to commercialisation, industry and investor demand, and mentorship and community. Gender imbalance has also been noted. The report also highlights that the primary failures of startups stem from team instability and a lack of market fit/commercialisation skills, validating the need for the FOODITY Fund to focus on advanced, structural support.

The findings have helped shape the Unique Value Proposition (UVP) for the FOODITY Fund, which focuses on providing streamlined administration, tailored expert mentorship and meaningful direct industry and investor connections to bridge the gap from innovation to commercial success for advanced food and nutrition startups.

1 Introduction

The [FOODITY project](#) aims to support digital and data-driven solutions that promote sustainable food systems while upholding citizen data sovereignty. Following two successful pilot programmes, the FOODITY consortium is conceptualising a new FOODITY Fund to continue its mission post-project. To ensure the fund effectively meets the needs of its target beneficiaries, a qualitative research approach, specifically semi-structured interviews, was adopted to gather insights directly from startups experienced in seeking and receiving funding.

2 Method

To understand the intricacies of startup funding experiences, as well as mentor and investor experiences in VCs, accelerators and incubators, a series of semi-structured interviews were conducted. A pre-defined set of interview questions was developed to guide the conversations, ensuring consistency across interviews while allowing for flexibility to explore emergent themes. The questions were verified by an exploitation expert via the Horizon Europe Booster service. The interview style was intentionally semi-informal, encouraging participants to offer insights and comments beyond the pre-set questions. However, it was observed that most interviewees did not volunteer additional comments beyond the direct questions posed. The duration of the interviews varied, ranging from approximately 30 minutes to a maximum of one hour.

Participants were recruited through established professional networks and existing project collaborations. A total of six startups and four mentors and investors were interviewed for this analysis outside of grantees that participated in the FOODITY Pilot Programme given their feedback was incorporated into research through surveys and workshops. The gender composition of the interviewed founders was predominantly male, with five male founders and one female founder participating. The gender composition of mentors and investors included two females and two males. The collected interview data were transcribed and then subjected to a thematic analysis, a systematic process for identifying, analysing and reporting patterns (themes) within data, allowing for the extraction of key insights, challenges and desired support mechanisms from the startups' perspectives.

3 Key Themes and Conclusions

The qualitative analysis revealed several critical themes that directly inform the design and value proposition of the FOODITY Fund.

3.1 Bureaucratic and Administrative Burden

A significant pain point across multiple interviews is the excessive paperwork and reporting requirements associated with grants, particularly from EU-funded programmes. All startups felt that it is an administrative burden and that reports require an inappropriate level of detail and technicality. The process of collecting signatures from multiple partners to submit a proposal, for example, especially from universities, is particularly difficult and time-consuming. Part of this burden comes from having different mentalities and approaches to developing a technological product.

Although the process of actually assembling documents and submitting them via platforms like F6S, for example, the efforts involved in searching for appropriate funding calls and preparing proposals can be extremely time consuming and challenging. In some cases, startups have opted for external consultants to prepare proposals. In other cases, startups apply to as many funds as possible rather than a selective few that are more aligned. It is therefore possible that startups tweak their positioning and goals to match prospective funds.

The internal operational processes in academia versus a business also vary greatly. Pre-application support services for developing consortia between startups and research institutions should be considered.

The perception was that reporting often felt more like surveillance rather than an appropriate form of monitoring and support. A suggested improvement was to provide report templates at the outset of the project to help manage expectations and make the reporting process easier. Additionally, some startups spoke about reports not being read. It remains unclear how effective reports are at accessing startup progress.

The FOODITY Fund should explore alternative approaches to monitoring startup performance rather than required reporting. Basic reports – which should be kept to a minimum – that outline performance against pre-determined KPIs may still be an appropriate path forward. However, beyond this, it may be more effective to have programme managers and assigned mentors interact with the products/prototypes being developed as that is clear evidence of progress.

- "Definitely, signing all this [required paperwork to submit a proposal] before [being accepted to the programme], circulating through all partners to sign it...to provide all these details and signing things [was] totally unnecessary." – Startup 3

- “[The reports] feels a bit like a tick-the-box...I spent a lot of time in the past weeks on writing reports on the KPIs that we agreed on, but I don't feel like it's been read...[because] in these documents [there] are certain links that go to a drive that we have and there I can see that these links haven't been opened.” – Startup 1
- “..sometimes you need to write long reports, like what each person did in each month. That's very painful. It just takes a lot of time, and in the end, all the things that take a lot of time are not going to be done by humans but by AI because if you have 30 startups in a programme and you have five people working for each startup and you have a 12-month long programme, that's 1,800 reports..nobody's going to read that.” – Startup 4
- “Imagine as a startup, you always need money...[And it's really hard to] understand how the European funding works when you are not inside this business...You don't understand where you have to go; the calls are not always easy to understand.” – Startup 2

3.2 Training and Cohort Misalignment

The majority of startups spoke about training content that was not tailored to their specific stage of development, often encountering entry-level training when they are at a much more advanced stage. This was largely attributed to cohorts comprising companies at vastly different maturity levels.

The ideal scenario would be a "plug-and-play programme" where startups can choose relevant modules and workshops. It is also important to have structured programmes that cater to specific stages such that startups are working together in cohorts that are in similar stages and facing similar challenges. This not only allows for only relevant training to be made available, but also for startups to work together by learning how to tackle overlapping problems.

- "We were part of one accelerator where in the description of the accelerator..you expect it's an accelerator for companies that are a little bit older, have a product, have some knowledge, but at the end, we end up..in sessions which explained basic things from zero [which were] totally unacceptable topics for us and for other startups." – Startup 3
- "Not all the trainings were useless, but of course, when you join several of these programmes, you have stuff that repeats..." – Startup 5
- “...[to have] a successful accelerator programme..you need kind of equals in the group because if you have companies that just signed their entity and you have companies that are going for the second fundraising round, the gap is just too big and [after the first two years you need different things and different people]...It takes time from the entrepreneur as well. And that's time that you're not spending on sales or things that bring...that return on investment...What I've seen from my own experience, if I notice that the quality of..the workshops or the teachers or the mentors is not as high as what I need..then I'm going to spend my time on other things.” – Startup 1

3.3 Gap from Innovation to Commercialisation

A prominent theme, particularly from later-stage startups and mentors/investors, was the significant funding and support gap between achieving a high Technology Readiness Level (TRL 7) and successfully bringing a product to market (TRL 9), as well as market and regulatory hurdles. Existing programmes often focus on innovation and development, i.e. TRL 1 - 6, leaving startups in a precarious position for commercialisation. While research is often sound, innovation often "crashes" in the market due to the weak marketplace for new innovations in Europe.

- "Where we see a lot of innovation, unfortunately, crashing is..in the market, meaning that they [startups] might reach the first sales, but then the scale-up is extremely, extremely difficult." – Mentor/Investor 1

It is important to note that several accelerator programmes already do exist for advanced startups.¹ Although there are fewer programmes focused on advanced startups with direct investor connections², it is possible that many entry-stage startups are unaware of opportunities or lack the necessary developments to become strong candidates for these other competitive programmes.

- "The only thing is after you develop to TRL 7, what do you do then? Because I have seen in my history a lot of cases where you develop a very nice technology, you reach TRL 7, and then you don't go to the market because you don't have the financing...It's very important to fill this funding gap because you have a product, which is already..demonstrated, it's validated, it's ready, but it's not a real product, and that means that you may not have the capacity in terms of knowledge and in terms of money to bring it to the market." – Startup 6
- "...the issue with all of these grant programmes is the sustainability...So [the issue was raised with] our startup and others that what's next once [our accelerator programme] is over? How do we continue to sustain what we've built? And in our case, this is also true because the revenues that we have right now from the paying users is not enough to keep it up and continue developing it." – Startup 5

When it comes to the food and nutrition sectors specifically, regulatory roadblocks are also a barrier to commercialisation. For example, new foods like insect-based proteins, fail to match the price of current commodities. Fundamental shifts in business modelling is required to overcome such a hurdle beyond the research and development phase. This also means mentors must work hard in supporting startups to navigate complex regulations when developing their go-to-market strategies.

¹ [EIC Accelerator](#); [EIT Food RisingFoodStars](#); [Eatable Adventures](#); [Kickstart Innovation](#)

² https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-2025-work-programme_en; <https://agfundernews.com/why-is-europe-behind-in-food-tech-investment>

- “If we concentrate on the food space, one [thing] is very clear, [which is that regulation is] quite difficult..because we have a lot of nice projects, good ingredients, health ingredients, safe ingredients and we cannot commercialise it in Europe...I'm coordinating the Healthy Aging Think and Do Tank for the EIT Food, where we have academia, companies like Danone and many different people from different environments..[with] like minds, very strong..and very experienced. And there are a lot of ideas, but most of them, you need to say..‘we can't do this: it's a new claim; it's a new food, novel food’, and so on...Then the second thing is go-to-market...not always, but many times, we have very technical people inside the organisation, and they don't know exactly how to reach the market, which geography to choose. So, it also goes in relation with regulatory affairs. You need to have a clear strategy that aligns both if your project is very novel.” – Investor/Mentor 3

3.4 Industry and Investor Demand

All startups expressed the need for funding programmes to facilitate direct matchmaking with industry partners for market access and with investors for follow-up funding rounds. This goes beyond mere networking opportunities. Accelerator programmes tend to be focused on standard entry-level training models and themselves have little to no direct connections to important industry players. Therefore, it is essential that future funding programmes are grounded in strong networks connecting research/academia with industry, investors and startups. Otherwise, the gaps between academia and industry, as well as the gaps between startups and corporations will continue to persist.

However, it is also important to note that direct investor and industry connections are more prominent in funding programmes that are aimed towards advanced startups rather than entry-level support.³

- "I personally very much like when industry is involved. I think that's very good when the industry is setting up challenges and when there is the opportunity to meet industrial access within the programme...So, if the programme is well-designed [such that it] will get you to the customer, and that's why I also think that involvement of industry is crucial." – Startup 4
- "The fundraising part should be emphasised in terms of not only the grants...But also, there should be matchmaking with investors and helping these startups to prepare for meetings with investors to pitch their idea, to work on it.." – Startup 5

³ <https://eicscalingclub.eu/>

3.5 Mentorship and Community

Some startups felt that general mentorship was not useful, however, in cases where mentors were paired according to expertise and needs and worked closely with a given startup, this was seen as highly valuable. It is crucial that mentors not just have the required expertise to assist startups but also have experience (or training) in the mentoring process itself. Another interesting point is payment. One startup mentioned that great mentors will not work for low fees, which may be part of the reason why many mentoring schemes are unhelpful. It is important to ensure that any funding programme is able to pay prospective mentors properly.

From the perspective of mentors and investors, mentoring may be seen as an important relationship to ensure startup success. In some cases, mentors become a temporary part of the team or end up buying shares of the company. When it comes to payment for services, it is highly variable. Some mentors are paid through an existing fund and/or programme, which can often be too low. Fees also depend on geographic location. It is important for any future fund to enable fair payment for such services. However, mentors provide these services in some cases because the experience itself can be very rewarding. In other words, altruism serves as the emotional reward of helping startups and can play a key motivating factor beyond financial benefits.^{4 5}

- If you ask me what benefit I get from a personal perspective is I love the sector. I love being in touch with people and talking with people around the world about their startups, their problems, because at the end of the day, I've done that before and obviously every project is different, but there is like a good connection normally with CEOs that really want to have a mentor because they value that you have done the same...And sometimes you wear your suit and sometimes you need to do other stuff...So from a personal perspective it's very enriching." - Mentor/Investor 3

The importance of peer-to-peer support and community among startups, although only emphasised by one interviewee, is also an important aspect of accelerator programmes to consider. When given the appropriate space and opportunity to collaborate and support one another, communities can become an integral part of growth and development.⁶

A couple of interviews mentioned the use of a Telegram group during their participation in a food accelerator programme. This served as a useful tool to connect with other startups who may have been facing similar issues and provide peer support and knowledge sharing. A future funding programme should consider implementing such a structure to facilitate peer-to-peer startup support that may continue post-programme.

⁴ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/392201022_How_Does_Mentoring_Startup_Founders_Influence_Early-Stage_Venture_Progress

⁵ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321231046_Mentoring_in_Startup_Ecosystems

⁶ https://mackinstitute.wharton.upenn.edu/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/Winston-Smith-Sheryl-Hannigan-Thomas-and-Gasiorowski-Laura_Peering-Inside.How-do-Peer-Effects-Impact-Entrepreneurial-Outcomes-in-Accelerators.pdf; <https://jums.ub.uni-muenchen.de/JMS/article/view/5267>

- “I think mentorship – matching the startup with the right mentor – is an important element. Also, peer-to-peer mentorship with the other startups that are engaged in this programme, matching with a big industry or someone to bring it to the market.” – Startup 5
- “I think it's better to have a cohort of companies that are in different sectors, but in the same stage..than the other way around...Also from different sectors you can learn a lot..so although right now maybe you're not working in the same sector..maybe your company will evolve and you will evolve as an entrepreneur..[and then] connect later on. I still have contacts with several of the entrepreneurs that were with me in that programme in 2019.” – Startup 1
- “But I think that it's good to have a pool of mentors which we can then choose from. For example, if we need someone to sort out our website or social media channels, or if we need someone to help us with legal documents. But not to have that as an obligation, but to be able to choose who we're going to work with.” – Startup 4

3.6 Investment Priorities and Team Stability

Investors and mentors prioritise the founding team's capacity to manage and scale, citing poor team dynamics as a major reason for startup failure. In other words, people are the key risk: the greatest concern regarding Return on Investment (ROI) is not the market, but the people running the company, especially at the seed phase. Failure often occurs because the team breaks down sometime along the road. There can also be a scaling gap in which founders must quickly shift to a managerial role over a short period (e.g. five to 100 people over two years).

- “If startups fail, especially in the seed phase, [it's because of] people, [they] are the key to the success of startups and not the business itself...”. – Investor/Mentor 2

It is also inevitable that many startups will not make it to market. Therefore, investors take decisions with the understanding that not all investments will lead to profit. Responses suggest that there may be misalignment with startup and investor priorities. Whereas many startups are focused on getting funding and investment, investors evaluate team composition, proven minimum viable product (MVP) or evidence of traction with users/clients that showcase a demand for their product, even if the revenue is not yet there.

- “...between 30 and 60% of seed stage startups will not get to series A – like every other series A startup will not get to series B. And after series B, it's..complete markets, growth capital. So, it changes everything. [It's]..classic portfolio management. You invest in 20 startups that half of them are worth zero, and you hope that in the other 10, there's one fund returner and then more from the remaining nine.” – Investor/Mentor 4

3.7 Gender

It is interesting to note that all startups spoke about having a mixed gender core team with women in leadership roles. However, it is also worth noting that only one woman participated in the six interviews. Although this could be due to chance and six is far from a representative sample size, this reflects a systemic issue with gender equality.⁷ Whilst the roles of women in these startups is not questioned, it may not be mere coincidence that the person with whom initial contact was made and then proceeded to be interviewed was male for majority of these interviews.

Should a future fund require that startups have gender balanced teams and/or are led by women? The landscape currently does not cater to such a reality and demanding this within a problematic system may not be the most appropriate solution.

Although all EU funding calls now require gender to be addressed whether in the composition of given consortia and/or in the third party funding calls⁸, this expectation may not realistically reflect reality. It must be recognised that especially in the tech startup and accelerator space, these sectors are largely male dominated still. For example, it cannot be ignored that the majority of investments go to all-male founding teams.⁹

Whilst the proposed FOODITY Fund should encourage gender balance, wider efforts that go far beyond this must be in place to change harmful gender biases and enable systemic changes towards gender inclusion. The FOODITY Fund could, for example, work with other entities to train prospective female mentors and work with other entities to establish investor and industry networks with gender quotas.¹⁰

⁷ <https://www.pwc.co.uk/who-we-are/leadership-and-people/inclusion/her-tech-talent/time-to-close-the-gender-gap.html>;
<https://www.eit.europa.eu/news-events/news/only-15-seed-funding-goes-women-led-deep-tech-start-ups-reveals-new-study>

⁸ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/democracy-and-rights/gender-equality-research-and-innovation_en

⁹ <https://ff.co/women-funding-statistics-2025/>

¹⁰ <https://www.aiprm.com/women-in-tech-statistics/>

4 FOODITY Fund's Unique Value Proposition (UVP)

Based on research, including these interviews, surveys and FOODITY awardee feedback (via surveys¹¹ and workshops), it is clear that the FOODITY Fund should **help advanced food and nutrition startups by providing a streamlined funding opportunity with simplified administration, tailored expert mentorship and meaningful and direct industry and investor connections, as well as go-to-market training, to bridge the gap from innovation to commercial success.**

The FOODITY Pilot Programme required SMEs/startups to match with a social innovation partner and develop a consortium with expertise in citizen engagement. Although some applicants during both of FOODITY's open calls struggled to find appropriate partners, interviewees did not express difficulties in finding partners to align with the call. The issue is a wider, systemic one in which businesses operate at different speeds and with vastly different mentalities and approaches than non-profits and academia. Although a given accelerator cannot solve this issue on a systemic level, this further emphasises the need to streamline bureaucratic processes with pre-application support on how to collaborate.

This Unique Value Proposition (UVP) directly addresses the most pressing needs and desires articulated by the interviewed startups:

- **Advanced food and nutrition startups:** Addressing the demand to cater to later-stage startups (TRL 7-9) and tailored support for companies beyond the initial conceptualisation phase, ensuring the programme's relevance. It also ensures proper support given many existing accelerators and third party funding opportunities within EU-funded projects are more focused on early-stage startups.
- **Streamlined funding opportunity with simplified administration:** Often the complexity of applications deter promising startups from applying and complex administrative and reporting procedures during the funding programme take away from crucial scaling activities.
- **Tailored expert mentorship:** Generic training, especially sessions focused on beginner-level knowledge (e.g. the business model canvas), offer little value to more advanced startups. It is vital to provide tailored and individualised sessions that are focused on the specific needs of a given startup. In addition, being paired with the right mentors ensures that startups are receiving direct support for specific pain points. Mentors must be chosen carefully, not only factoring in their expertise and alignment with the given startup, but also display knowledge of how the mentoring process works or else go through training on *how* to mentor.

¹¹ A total of 20 survey responses were collected during the research phase, which were not enough to complete a statistical analysis.

- **Direct industry and investor connections:** Startups often lack direct connections to industry and investors during their participation in accelerator programmes. Providing structured pathways to market, including facilitating such connections and allowing startups to build their networks is also crucial.
- **Moving from innovation to commercialisation:** Many startups are able to successfully move from ideation to prototyping. There is a gap, however, in enabling a given developed technology to enter the market. Alongside support in connecting with industry and investors, it is important to work with startups to pave the pathway for market entry, especially in markets that are difficult to penetrate.

5 Conclusion

The qualitative analysis of startup and mentor/investor interviews provides important insights on how the future FOODITY Fund should be structured. By prioritising simplified administration, bespoke mentorship and direct connections to industry and investors, the FOODITY Fund has the potential to effectively support advanced startups in their journey from innovative solutions to sustainable commercial success, thereby contributing significantly to the project's overarching goals for sustainable food systems.

Annex 1: Startup Interview Questions

1. Tell me about your fundraising process and the last time that you needed funding.
2. Can you tell me about the types of funding programmes and accelerators that you've applied to in the past five years, with a particular focus on food and nutrition?
3. What is the total amount of funding that you've received in this period?
4. When it comes to common challenges and successes in funding programmes, what comes to mind when you reflect on your experience?
5. How well did the requirements of the funding programmes that you applied for align with the goals and needs of your startup?
6. Building off what was previously said, can you further describe your internal process for fundraising?
7. Can you describe your rationale behind selecting your team members when you apply for funding? And did you apply as a single entity or as a consortium? What factors do you consider when putting a consortium together?
8. How much time did your team spend preparing your most recent funding proposal? Which part of the proposal did you spend the most time working on?
9. Regarding the administrative aspects of applying for funding and also managing the funds, what specific elements or processes have worked well for you? What were the biggest challenges you faced in terms of administration, reporting, or any friction during the funding process?
10. When you did successfully receive funding, what specific support or activities from these programmes, beyond just the money, were most useful in developing your product/solution?
11. If you could design a future funding scheme for food and nutrition startups, what specific requirements or benefits would you consider to be the most important?
12. Can you talk about the gender composition of the key team members in the last fund that you applied for?
13. Have any of the funding schemes you've applied to or been a part of required you to give up equity? If so, what were the conditions? If not, what conditions would be required for you to consider equity funding?
14. Is there anything else you'd like to share?

Annex 2: Investor Interview Questions

1. To start, could you walk me through your typical process for identifying and sourcing potential projects or startups to invest in within the food and nutrition sector? What are your preferred channels for finding new opportunities?
2. When you're assessing a project's potential, what are the primary criteria or key performance indicators (KPIs) you look for? How do you typically weigh these factors in your decision-making?
3. How do you currently manage your deal flow – from initial contact to due diligence? Do you use any specific tools, software or platforms?
4. Let's talk about the challenges. When you make an investment, what are some of the biggest risks or concerns you have regarding the project not meeting your expected Return on Investment (ROI)? What typically contributes to this happening?
5. (Follow-up if needed): Could you recall a specific situation where an investment underperformed on ROI? What were the key contributing factors or red flags you encountered?
6. Beyond ROI, what are other significant pain points or frustrations you encounter during the post-investment phase?
7. Describe the tracking and verification process for outputs, milestones and impact of projects that you've invested in.
8. Assuming that you have a 200K budget to address all previously mentioned challenges, how would you use them?
9. What do you value most in terms of visibility and profile raising?
10. Describe benchmarking data or insights into macro-trends with the food and nutrition landscape that have been useful for your decision-making and how you access those insights and data.
11. Do you currently use any post-investment support, reporting automation or monitoring tools for long-term monitoring? Please describe them if so and how they support your work.
12. Finally, if you had to pick, what would be your top 1 or 2 priorities for a food and nutrition fund to truly succeed in addressing your needs and helping you achieve your investment goals?
13. Anything else you'd like to share?

Annex 3: Mentor Interview Questions

1. Tell me about your experience working with startups.
2. What are the biggest challenges your startups face?
3. How do startups approach you for mentorship? How do you get matched with startups if you work with them through an accelerator/incubator or funding programme?
4. How do you access a startups' progress, impact and outputs?
5. Have you ever had equity, royalty or share agreements?
6. Do you know approximately how many startups you've mentored that have gone on to secure investment?
7. Are you part of a mentor network? If so, can you tell me the name?
8. If so, what benefits, if any, do you receive from this network?
9. If so, how long have you been part of this network?
10. Do you get paid for your work and if so, are you able to discuss how much?
11. Anything else you'd like to share?